

STUDY OF THE INFLUENCE OF ULTRASOUND ON THE PROCESS OF
ADSORPTION PURIFICATION OF PARAFFIN

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Annotation: It is known that, depending on the mineralogical and chemical composition, clay adsorbents have different sizes and pore volumes, and their filling requires the selection of rational frequencies of ultrasonic vibrations. Currently, the following types of clay adsorbents are mainly used in the oil refining industry: Opaque clay adsorbents of the Navoi region: Kermin, bentonite clay adsorbents of the Navbahor field and palygorskite clay adsorbents of the same field.

Key words: Mineralogical and chemical composition of paraffins, ultrasonic vibration frequency, clarity of paraffin, Model-200 mercury pyrometer, Opoka clay from Carmine mine, Alkakine bentonite of Navbahor mine, Carbonate polygorsite of Navbahor mine.

Table 3.3.1 lists the chemical composition of the above adsorbents.

Table 3.3.1

Chemical components	Content, in absolute dry matter %		
	Opoka clay from Kermin mine	Alkakine bentonite of Navbahor mine	Carbonate polygorsite of Navbahor mine
Al ₂ O ₃	9,35	13,69	8,63
FeO	0,5	-	3,41
Fe ₂ O ₃	3,55	5,1	-
CaO	13,56	0,48	10,08
TiO ₂	0,3	0,35	-
MgO	3,48	1,84	2,74
Na ₂ O	3,06	1,53	-
K ₂ O	1,25	1,75	1,6

P ₂ O ₃	-	0,43	1,99
SO ₃	3,9	0,75	-
P.P.P	10,10	16,17	24,33
SiO ₂	50,8	57,91	46,79
Total	99.85	99.98	99.75

Chemical composition of clay adsorbents used in the purification of paraffins Table 3.3.1 shows that with a change in the type of adsorbent, i.e. its mineralogical composition and chemical composition also change significantly. For example, bentonite adsorbent contains Cao-0.48%, polygorskite adsorbent - 10.08%, Kermin mine Opoka clay contains 13.56%. All these differences, of course, are reflected in the size and volume of their pores.

With this in mind, we investigated the porosity of selected clay adsorbents and, in particular, the volumes of transition pores. Analyzes were performed in a standard method on a Model-200 mercury pyrometer (Colbo Erba strumantazione, Italy). At the same time, the duration of the study is 30 minutes, the minimum pressure of the introduced mercury is 20x10⁵ kPa, and the mass of the studied clays is 0.977g each. The bleaching ability of clay adsorbents depends on the conditions of their contact with paraffin. In this regard, the frequency of ultrasonic vibrations also plays an important role in the purification of paraffins with clay adsorbents. We studied the effect of ultrasonic vibration frequency on wax clarity at 80-850C. In this case, the duration of experiments was 60 minutes, and the amount of clay adsorbents entered was equal to 4.0% by weight of paraffin. The results of experimental studies are shown in Figure 3.3.1.

Figure 3.3.1.

Opoka adsorbent; bentonite adsorbent; palygorskite adsorbent.

Figure 3.3.1. Variation of the light level of paraffin (S) depending on the frequency of ultrasound vibration (H).

As can be seen from this figure, it is reasonable to choose the working range of the ultrasonic frequency for the opac-like adsorbent of the Kermin mine within the following limits: from 15 to 20 kHz, for the alkaline bentonite of the Navbahor mine - from 20 to 25 kHz, and for the carbonate palygorskite of the Navbahor mine - 25 to 30 kHz.

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